

Lessons in Effective Team Science Processes: A Case Study from Renaissance Computing Institute

By: Brandy L. Farlow, M.A.(bfarlow@renci.org); Amanda C. Miller, M.A.(amiller@renci.org); Stephanie N. Suber, M.S. (subers@renci.org); and Joanna O. Mieczkowska, M.A. (asia@renci.org)

Abstract

Team science is increasingly important in research and innovation,¹ bringing together experts from diverse disciplines to solve complex problems. In a 2010 article, Falk-Krzesinski, Börner, et al. expressed that “public health, social, technological, and environmental problems that impact our world are complex,” and “the sophistication of these challenges necessitates cross-disciplinary engagement and collaboration, and the longer-term interaction of groups of investigators—what is termed team science.”² Effective team processes around communication, people management, project management, and collaborative processes among team members with different skill sets, backgrounds, and perspectives are critical for successful team science.³

The Renaissance Computing Institute (RENCI) at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill has built practical knowledge in this field for years. During the Spring of 2023, RENCI Team Science Group created a staff survey to evaluate awareness and usage of team science principles. The survey intentionally did not use the term “team science.” Instead, it anonymously explored staff perspectives and lessons learned from RENCI’s history of coordinating “large,

The majority of survey respondents had been with RENCI for over 7 years. Only 4 respondents had been with the organization between 1 and 3 years. The distinction between 0-1 and 1-3 years is due to the steep learning curve individuals experience in their first year with the organization. Interestingly, this may explain recognition of the term “team science.” When asked how they might describe large group collaborations (in and beyond science) to a friend or colleague, twenty respondents answered, with 6 specifically mentioning team science (three from the 7+ years group, two from 1-3 years, and one from 3-7 years). Only two RENCI employees from 0-1 years responded to this question, and neither mentioned team science. All responses are reflected in the words cloud above. Note: text sizes do not represent frequency.

collaborative, multidisciplinary groups in science-related pursuits.” Using the survey results, this white paper explores RENCi’s challenges and successes as a case study of team science in action.

Data from the RENCi 2023 survey reinforce the team science literature, illustrating that clear communication, defined roles and responsibilities, trust, and mutual respect are the most effective ways to shape and manage effective teams. The survey data also showcases how effective team processes and dynamics can be challenging to achieve, particularly when teams are composed of individuals with different backgrounds, perspectives, locations, and expertise.

Through this white paper, we highlight RENCi-specific successes and lessons learned. By promoting these lessons in effective team processes and dynamics, we hope to engage with the team science research community to collaboratively tackle some of the most significant challenges facing society today.

Introduction

This study investigated RENCi’s challenges and successes in large team science-based collaborations, trying to understand the keys to our successful projects, while working to mitigate potential future difficulties. RENCi develops and deploys data science cyberinfrastructure across multiple domains, helping researchers in academia, government, and business use data to drive discoveries, innovate, make informed decisions, and spur economic development. The institute’s project variety - and their increasing size, complexity, and broadening geographical span in the last five years - provided opportunities to explore team science best practices.

While the science of team science is fairly new, team collaboration research is prevalent in many fields that pre-date it. Modifying currently used practices in business,⁴ technology,⁵ athletics,⁶ and the humanities⁷ (specifically project management, agile methodology, conflict resolution, and communication, etc.), and applying them to scientific teams may help numerous team science inquiries, while providing team science practitioners a path to move forward. As such, many of the results in our survey suggested a heavy emphasis on collaborative practices gleaned from the wealth of information in other fields.

Materials and Methods

All 121 RENCi employees received a Google Forms survey on April 12, 2023 and were given until May 16, 2023 to respond. The survey allowed anonymous and selective responsiveness to questions. Thirty individuals responded, yielding a 25% response rate. The survey questioned respondents about their descriptive information (e.g., role, number of years at RENCi), their

team science experiences (e.g., lessons learned, challenges), and their understanding of collaborative practices (e.g., changes in approach to team building).

A Qualitative Data Analyst analyzed survey results using the qualitative data analysis software NVivo, version 12, with an inductive approach where codes and themes emerged as the survey responses were read.

Results

Responses were not incentivized, but the survey’s 30 respondents accounted for individuals across all RENCi teams. This group reported variable longevity with the organization and collectively worked on over 60 unique collaborative projects in their time at RENCi.

Team Science Challenges and Lessons Learned

RENCi often works with large-team data science initiatives. According to respondents, after logistics, success or failure depends on the right mix of personalities, but RENCi anticipates work style and personality challenges and tries to make people feel heard. These ventures are still not without their challenges. Respondents noted several challenges and lessons learned particular to our projects’ large size and scope:

Category	Challenge	Lessons Learned
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lost time due to miscommunication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain regular communication, even if people would prefer fewer meetings. Develop a common vocabulary. Communicate project goals early, and clearly assign thought leaders, action items, and responsibilities. Agree on communication tools (Teams, Slack, email, etc.), and use them consistently. Be transparent about project decisions and approaches.
Document Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multiple approvals for final product/deliverable submission Large document volume creates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish simple, user-friendly documentation processes early, including naming conventions, storage locations, and orientation, and share them with new members.

Category	Challenge	Lessons Learned
	difficulty finding specific documents	
Organizational Struggles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coordination difficulties, because “It is not possible to know who is doing what.” ● People management: expectations, decision-making, and productive relationship building ● Emphasis on technical/scientific tasks creates a lack of time for administrative tasks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use Project Managers (PMs): An involved project manager “can help a project go from struggling to successful and help everyone's sanity along the way.” ● Help the team anticipate and manage challenging collaborators and clients ● Don’t make people “stay in their lane”
Human Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competing priorities from different organizations, institutions, or subteams ● “Keeping track of the big picture” ● “Learning to work together and setting aside our own ego for the larger good” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Combine the right strengths, experience, and work styles ● Break large teams into smaller units ● Get everyone working toward the project goals ● Provide time for learning and development ● Be flexible and adaptable ● Be aware of team needs. Listen, and be receptive to different viewpoints ● Be open minded in discussions with other disciplines ● “Don’t argue, debate” ● Know your limitations ● Learn from mistakes and apply these lessons in the future

“The PMs [Project Managers] I have worked with are really good at synthesizing information, organizing large groups and orienting to specific

tasks, keeping agendas and times on point, and summarizing action items and next steps. I know that the PMs will...schedule meetings...action items will be assigned and reviewed, detailed notes are taken, and follow-up is done. This allows me to focus on tasks, expanding collaborations, providing technical support, or other as-needed items.”

Perceptions and Understanding of Teams

Respondents were asked to discuss changes in their understanding of large group collaboration, team work, and team building. These questions had a 50% (building teams) and 60% (approaching teamwork) response rate, with employees of seven or more years at RENCi providing the majority of responses.

Building Teams

Several respondents considered individual employee skill sets and put thought into “personalities and styles” when staffing a project. This includes finding people with complementary skills and striking a balance between “standard” and “free thinkers,” ultimately benefiting work quality and promoting a more successful team dynamic.

“Your most powerful asset is the people you haven’t hired yet. Hire good people – change the culture to be the culture you want.”

Other ideas included creating mentorship opportunities and making individual team members feel valued. One respondent championed thoughtful team member selection, saying to look for:

“...people who are flexible, willing to consider alternate options, willing to say no when needed, willing to put in the work to get something done but at the same time [setting] boundaries and parameters that are realistic, and have strong communication skills.”

Approaches to Teamwork

“I’ve...learned to set aside my ego more and focus on what is best for the common good and less for just me/my team”

As team members have different backgrounds and disciplines, “clarity and flexibility” are essential to “create [a] healthy and productive environment,” based upon mutual respect. Flexibility, listening to and supporting team members, and focusing on what benefits the whole

team are particularly important in large teams where, despite establishing well-defined roles, the dynamics are constantly evolving.

Several individuals noted the importance of detailed onboarding and succession planning, including thorough technical documentation, particularly as these pertain to staff turnover.

Limitations

As a voluntary survey, some self-selection bias is possible. For example, while responses came from all longevities at RENCI, most came from those who have been with the organization for 7+ years (43%) and 0-1 years (23%). This may be because long-term employees were the most willing participants, while newer employees may compare the organization with their recent experience elsewhere. Responses were lowest from those in the 1-3 year range, accounting for just under 14% of the responses.

Respondents were asked: “On a scale of 1 to 10 (1 being never, and 10 being always), how often do you work on large, collaborative, multidisciplinary projects in your work at RENCI?” This represents the average responses from each longevity grouping. It should be noted that all groupings, aside from the 7+ year group, included respondents from teams whose position requires them to be more hands-on with projects by nature of their position (for example, finance team members).

While many respondents indicated regular participation in team science at RENCi, some responses reflected little interaction. For example, the 1-3 year group averaged 6.5 (on a scale of 1-10) for participation frequency. This group's low responses are partly due to the group's few respondents. Unfortunately, the survey also did not account for teams that rarely interact collaboratively outside RENCi. These individuals include (among others), members of the finance and internal technology teams. Responses from these groups skewed participation frequency averages.

Self-reporting can also create bias. One additional notable outlier presented in the 3-7 year group, where a low response came from a member of a particular RENCi team, despite most of the team's projects boasting multiple research partners and collaborators across academia and government.⁸ Due to the survey's anonymity, it is hard to gain understanding.

Key Themes

From the survey, the following key ideas seem vital to RENCi's participation in team science and may benefit others who seek to participate:

- **People:** Build a team with the right mix of personalities and expertise and make sure everyone feels heard and valued. Take note of team dynamics and be open to different working styles. Share common goals and set aside individual success/ego.
- **Documentation:** Follow best practices, including standard naming conventions to make documents easily accessible and findable; tracking team/work group member assignments, as it can be challenging to know who is doing what; and noting document revision history, making clear who has version control.
- **Communication:** Agree early on and use tools (e.g., Slack) consistently. Develop a common vocabulary. Take time to make sure everyone is on the same page.
- **Project Management:** Good and involved project managers can oversee all of the above. Leadership can foster a strong sense of community and belonging within large, diverse, interdisciplinary, collaborative teams. Every team member should be treated as an equal and every voice heard and considered. This type of environment facilitates scientific research and fosters novel ideas.

Additional Information

To view the poster from which this content was taken or to see additional information related to this study, view the [RENCi Team Science Shared Folder](#).

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